

1 **Nanoscale imaging of mobile carriers and trapped charges in**
2 **doped silicon p-n junctions**

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22 *Electronic Supplementary Information available*

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Abstract

Integrated circuits and certain silicon-based quantum computer architectures require the precise positioning of dopant nanostructures and hydrogen resist lithography can be used to fabricate such structures at the atomic-scale limit. However, there is no single technique capable of measuring the three-dimensional location and electrical characteristics of these dopant nanostructures, as well as the charge dynamics of carriers and trapped charges in their vicinity. Here we show that broad-band electrostatic force microscopy can be used for non-destructive carrier profiling of atomically-thin n-type (phosphorus) and p-type (boron) dopant layers in silicon, and their resulting p–n junctions. The probe has a lateral resolution of 10 nm and a vertical resolution of 0.5 nm, and detects the capacitive signature of sub-surface charges in a broad 1 kHz to 10 GHz frequency range. This allows the bias-dependent charge dynamics of free electrons in conducting channels, and trapped charges in oxide–silicon interfaces, to be investigated.

1 The patterned doping of silicon at the nanometre scale, for both classical and quantum applications, brings with it new
2 diagnostic challenges. For example, the visualisation and electrical characterisation of dopant structures within a single
3 transistor is difficult due to the reduced transistor size in current complementary metal–oxide–semiconductor (CMOS)
4 technology. This has serious implications for quality control and security in integrated circuit (IC) manufacturing,
5 where tampering of the local dopant profile has been shown to compromise IC integrity¹. Thus, the development of
6 techniques that can overcome current diagnostic limitations is essential^{2–4}. In particular, the development of a
7 technique capable of non-destructive, nanoscale measurements, as well as quantitative electrical characterisation,
8 would be valuable for both IC failure analysis⁵ and the creation of quantum architectures⁶ based on quantum confined
9 dopant nanostructures.

10 Using scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) hydrogen resist lithography, both acceptors⁷ and donors⁸ can be
11 patterned with atomic resolution into dopant nanostructures⁶ such as sheets⁹, wires¹⁰, and dots¹¹. This atomic resolution
12 doping has also been implemented in 3D structures¹² and can be integrated into a CMOS platform¹³. STM is, however,
13 relatively insensitive to the subsurface¹⁵ when used to measure such structures, though scanning microwave
14 microscopy (SMM) can be used non-destructively to determine the 3D-location of structures once they are buried
15 within the silicon wafer¹⁴.

16 In this Article, we show that donor–acceptor interface nanostructures can be fabricated by STM and then quantitatively
17 characterised using broad-band electrostatic force microscopy (bb-EFM). This technique can sense the impedance
18 gradient under different local biasing conditions across a broad frequency range from 1 kHz to 10 GHz, and offers a
19 factor of two improvement in lateral resolution and a factor of five improvement in sensitivity compared with SMM.
20 Quantitative finite element simulations, using a semiconductor drift-diffusion model, allow us to extract the vertical
21 distribution and polarity of the carriers with high confidence and without the need of a special calibration sample.
22 Furthermore, bb-EFM measurements made at varying frequencies allow us to estimate the density of oxide interface
23 trap states, which determine the performance of the final device¹⁶.

24 Unlike destructive imaging techniques — such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM)¹⁷, focused ion
25 beam scanning electron microscopy¹⁸, secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS)¹⁹, atom probe tomography
26 (APT), or scanning spreading resistance microscopy (SSRM)²⁰, which require milled, bevelled, or cross-
27 sectioned samples, EFM is non-destructive. The technique can also be performed in an ambient environment
28 using a standard atomic force microscope (AFM) with a lock-in amplifier and a signal generator. In addition,
29 measurements are performed in tapping mode, which provides an important advantage over SMM where the
30 best resolution requires the more invasive contact mode.

32 **Broad-band electrostatic force microscopy**

33 The bb-EFM setup is shown in Fig. 1 and its operation is fully explained in the Methods section. In brief, a
34 signal generator is connected to a conducting AFM probe. The electric potential V between the probe and the
35 sample deflects the cantilever under an electrostatic force F_{es} following the relation:

$$F_{es} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{dC^*}{dz} V^2 \quad (1)$$

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2 The complex capacitance gradient dC^*/dz , which we denote as C' , gives information on the local impedance
 3 below the tip and thus on the presence of dopants (changes of C' relative to an offset C'_0 are denoted as $\Delta C' =$
 4 $C' - C'_0$). Eq (1) simply states that the force is the derivative with respect to the probe-sample distance z of
 5 the energy CV^2 stored by the capacitor. For the particularly simple case of a parallel plate capacitor model,
 6 with plates of area A separated by a distance z , $C = A\epsilon/z$. For a fixed value of A and a dielectric permittivity, ϵ ,
 7 which is independent of z , $C' = -A\epsilon/z^2$. Thus, for given values of A and ϵ we can determine the distance z
 8 between the surface of a medium and a conducting plane produced e.g. by a delta doping layer below the
 9 surface. When applying an amplitude modulated electric field $V_{ac} = V_{ac,0} \cos(2\pi f_{mod} t) \cos(2\pi f_{carrier} t)$ with a
 10 carrier frequency $f_{carrier}$, and amplitude $V_{ac,0}$, we detect, with the lock-in amplifier, a cantilever oscillation at
 11 a frequency f_{mod} . The electrostatic force producing this deflection is a measure of the local tip-sample
 12 capacitance gradient²⁰

13

$$F_{es, \omega mod} = 1/4 |C'(V_{bias}, f_{carrier}, z)| V_{ac,0}^2 \quad (2)$$

14

15
 16 $F_{es, \omega mod}$ can then be studied as a function of V_{bias} and $f_{carrier}$. Note that $f_{carrier}$ is set independently from f_{mod} and
 17 is not influenced by cantilever mechanics. As a result, the frequency range available to bb-EFM (1kHz –
 18 10GHz) is orders of magnitude larger than those typically used in current sensing techniques like impedance
 19 microscopy^{22,23} (<10MHz), scanning capacitance microscopy²⁴ (1 MHz), scanning nonlinear dielectric
 20 microscopy²⁵ (1 GHz) or SMM^{14,26} (1-20GHz), all of which rely on a very narrowband matching of the
 21 electronic detection circuitry to achieve the required electrical sensitivity. Additionally, we note that the
 22 capacitance gradient C' signal offers more spatially localized information^{27,28}, and an improved electrical
 23 sensitivity, limited only by the thermal noise of the cantilever²⁹.

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25 Subsurface imaging and lateral resolution

26 Structures consisting of atomic layers (“ δ -layers”) of boron and phosphorus were patterned onto a Si(100)
 27 surface and subsequently encapsulated by a 15 nm thick epitaxial Si layer, as detailed in the Methods Section.
 28 Fig. 1 shows the resulting surface topography. In Fig. 2a, the same AFM tapping mode topography
 29 measurement is overlaid with simultaneously acquired EFM data. In Fig. 1 the surface topography is
 30 extremely flat (average roughness <1nm) and gives virtually no information about the dopant structure
 31 location. The encapsulation was therefore successful, and the applied electric field has no measurable impact
 32 on the topographic image. The superimposed electrostatic $\Delta C'$ image in Fig. 2a however displays an excellent
 33 contrast between the spatially averaged values of $\Delta C'_P = 0.40$ aF/nm and $\Delta C'_B = 0.25$ aF/nm, measured above

1 the nanostructured phosphorus and boron bars, and the surrounding Si substrate background. This
2 corresponds to a S/N ratio (SNR) of $\Delta C'_P/C'_{Noise} = 12$ and $\Delta C'_B/C'_{Noise} = 7$ (cf. lower profile line in Fig 2c),
3 six times better than SMM where we obtained $\Delta C'_P/C'_{Noise} = 2$ with an AFM-probe of comparable sharpness¹⁴.
4 One curious observation from Fig. 2a, explained in detail in the following section, is that the $\Delta C'$ signal
5 intensity from the B δ -layers is lower than for P δ -layers
6 Lateral resolution of the EFM has been estimated using patterned boron bars of decreasing widths, separated
7 by constant gaps of ~ 60 nm, as displayed in Fig. 2b and in Extended Data Figure 1 showing STM
8 measurement prior to encapsulation. The first two sets of two bars with widths of 32 nm and 16 nm are easily
9 resolved and a constant level in the middle of each bar is reached. The following 2x8 nm and 5x4 nm wide
10 bars are however only resolved as peaks, while thinner bars (i.e. 4 nm and 2 nm) are not resolved at all. The
11 line patterns on the right half of Fig. 2b, with 30 and 15 nm gaps, are nearly unresolved. Fitting a sum of two
12 logistic functions $f_{\text{logis}}(x) = A(1 + e^{-(x-x_0)/\delta})^{-1} - A(1 + e^{-(x-x_1)/\delta})^{-1}$ to the edges of the 32 nm and 16 nm bars
13 we calculate a lateral resolution of $2\delta = 10 \pm 5$ nm. This value is surprisingly good for a pattern buried 15 nm
14 below the surface and is approximately five times better lateral resolution than was achieved by SMM (cf.
15 $2\delta_{SMM} = 55\text{nm}$)¹⁴ using a similar sample and tip-apex radius ($R_{\text{apex,EFM}} = 26.4 \pm 0.2$ nm and $R_{\text{apex,SMM}} = 20 \pm 1$ nm)¹⁴,
16 for tip calibration see Extended Data Figure 2c and Methods section). A direct comparison of bb-EFM and
17 SMM on the same phosphorus patterned sample in Extended Data Figures 2-3 confirms these EFM results
18 ($2\delta = 13 \pm 2$ nm) and demonstrates that bb-EFM can clearly distinguish bars separated by 30 nm, while this is
19 impossible with SMM¹⁴. We expect the various measurement parameters to affect lateral resolution
20 differently in the force sensing (C') and current sensing (C) techniques. Modelling in Extended Data Figure
21 4 shows that while the tip radius has little impact here, the advantage of the C' measurement increases at
22 larger tip sample distance. In both models and experiments, the C' measurement exhibits maxima in both
23 lateral resolution and dopant contrast at a measurement frequency of ~ 10 -100 MHz (cf. Extended Data
24 Figures 4 and 5).

25

26 **Quantitative dopant profiling**

27 In addition to determining the lateral position of a patterned δ -layer, it is also important to measure its vertical position
28 and electrical characteristics. In particular, the carrier sign and concentration are key determinants of a device's
29 operational behaviour. Fig. 3c describes the bb-EFM contrast mechanism via the simplified equivalent circuit at
30 bottom left. For the Si regions without a δ -layer, an effective capacitance (air + oxide + depletion layer) in series with
31 the bulk resistance is formed below the tip. With the δ -layer present, this buried, highly conductive sheet acts as a 2-
32 dimensional electron gas (2DEG) capacitively coupled to the tip and bulk substrate in series. The AFM-probe apex
33 diameter R and distance z from the surface define the local field penetration depth below the surface, and the probed
34 sample volume. Application of a DC bias between sample and tip attracts or repels carriers depending on their sign,
35 and modulates the depletion capacitance under the tip depending on their concentration³⁰. Additionally, in the δ -layer

1 region, we assume that the bias modulates the occupation of δ -layer bands and therefore the 2DEG sheet resistance.
2 Measuring C' as a function of tip bias V_{bias} and the tip sample distance z , should therefore allow us to determine the
3 carrier type and vertical carrier concentration profile.

4 We show this quantification for a test sample containing six P δ -layer bars at two different depths and three different,
5 independently verified, dopant sheet densities ($\rho_{sh,1}=(2.87\pm 0.03)\times 10^{14}\text{ cm}^{-2}$, $\rho_{sh,2}=(6.23\pm 0.03)\times 10^{13}\text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $\rho_{sh,3} =$
6 $(1.86\pm 0.03)\times 10^{13}\text{ cm}^{-2}$)¹⁴ within an arsenic doped ($3\times 10^{14}\text{ cm}^{-3}$) Si wafer. Assuming a Gaussian δ -layer distribution
7 with $\sigma=1.5\text{ nm}$, this corresponds to a dopant concentration peak value $\rho=\rho_{sh}\sigma^{-1}(2\pi)^{-1/2}$, giving
8 $\rho_1=(7.63\pm 0.08)\times 10^{20}\text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\rho_2=(1.66\pm 0.08)\times 10^{20}\text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\rho_3=(0.49\pm 0.08)\times 10^{20}\text{ cm}^{-3}$. The P δ -layers are structured as
9 sketched in Fig. 3a, with their concentration maximum located at depths of $h_{nom}=(3.8\pm 0.1)\text{ nm}$ and $h_{nom}=(8.9\pm 0.1)\text{ nm}$,
10 as confirmed by SIMS measurements¹⁴. While the topography of the test sample is flat (see Supplementary Fig. 2) the
11 EFM image in Fig. 3a clearly visualizes the presence of the patterned bars. To extract the dopant profile we acquired
12 $C'(V_{bias})$ and $C'(z)$ curves at different positions on the sample. The Si $C'(V_{bias})$ curve in Fig. 3b, acquired over an area
13 with no δ -layer, resembles a classical high frequency capacitance versus voltage curve for n-type dopants, where we
14 find electron accumulation with high capacitance for high positive biases, depletion with reduced capacitance between
15 0-2V, and a further decrease of the capacitance in inversion. Acquiring the same curve on the P stripes, we find the
16 C' difference between accumulation and depletion/inversion is much lower compared to Si. Interestingly, the P bars
17 patterned with a low dopant density exhibit two decays, while the highly doped bars, at both 4nm and 9nm below the
18 surface, show only one. This is again in agreement with the picture of a highly doped δ -layer with low R_{sh} acting as
19 an electrically floating metallic plane in which the measured C' is dominated by the geometrical capacitance between
20 the probe and δ -layer. An applied DC bias modulates only the small epitaxial Si region between probe apex and δ -
21 layer, which has little impact on the overall signal, and results in a single decay in the $C'(V)$ curve (cf. Extended Data
22 Figure 6b). For a low doped δ -layer, the sheet-resistance is high and the geometrical capacitance plays a minor role; a
23 simpler, one-dimensional picture of a metal-insulator-semiconductor structure applies. Here, the depletion capacitance
24 $C_{si}(V)$ dominates while the increasingly negative applied bias pushes the depletion layer deeper into the substrate. The
25 resulting decays in the $C'(V)$ curve represent variations in the vertical dopant level (cf. Extended Data Figure 6).
26 The experimental $C'(z)$ approach curves in Fig. 3d indicate that the δ -layers can only be sensed when the AFM probe
27 is located very close to the surface ($z < 30\text{ nm}$). For distances above 50nm, most of the applied potential drops off in
28 the air gap between tip and sample, and $C'(z)$ curves acquired with and without δ -layers practically overlap.
29 Consequently, it is critical to carry out the electrical characterization of the δ -layers with low tapping amplitudes; for
30 our microscope, using PtSi-FM probes, amplitudes between 5 nm - 20 nm were optimal.

31 To quantitatively extract the active dopant profile from our measurements we developed a finite element model (FEM)
32 which captures the specific geometry and boundary conditions of the experimental arrangement and solves for the
33 potential (shown in Fig. 3c) and carrier distribution (details in Methods section). Using this model, we calculate
34 $C'(z, V, f, h, \rho)$ for a large range of values of the h and ρ parameters. Best fit h and ρ values for the measured δ -layer are
35 then extracted through comparison of the calculated and experimentally measured C' values.

1 This model is significantly more realistic than previous electrostatics-based FEM models¹⁴, and allows us to interpret
2 bias-dependent measurements. We note that the simulation is fully based on a drift diffusion model and therefore
3 cannot be used to explain quantum confinement effects that might be especially relevant at low temperatures where
4 medium and low doped silicon is not conductive. However, for measurements at ambient conditions, the doped silicon
5 semiconductor-model used here offers a good approximation. This can be seen from the calculated conduction band
6 profile of a P δ -layer shown in the inset of Fig. 3c. Here we indeed observe that only for high dopant densities
7 ($3 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, solid lines) does the effective conduction/donor band energy reside below the Fermi-level ($E_{CB} - E_F < 0$)
8 and thus acting like a floating metallic plane. A bias potential applied either to the tip, or the substrate only modifies
9 the energy profile in the silicon above the δ -layer. In contrast, for lower dopant concentrations ($3 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, dashed
10 lines) the applied bias also modulates the energy profile below the δ -layer.

11 Finally, for the determination of the dopant density profile we calculated $C'(V)$ and $C'(z)$ curves from the FEM model
12 and fit them to the experimental data. For the bare silicon data, the calculated $C'(V)$ curve fits very well, assuming a
13 tip work function³¹ of 5.7 eV and a tip radius of $R = 53 \pm 2$ nm, only slightly higher than the manufacturer specified
14 nominal tip radius. This agreement with simulation for the bare silicon confirms the conceptual viability of the model.

15 Using these fixed values of the tip radius and work function parameters, the dopant density ρ and layer depth h are
16 then extracted from the P δ -layer region measurements. The results are summarized in Table 1. The $C'(V)$ curves
17 allow extraction of dopant concentration with high confidence, while dopant depth h is extracted with lower
18 confidence. The contrary is the case for the $C'(z)$ curves where the dopant depth and concentration are estimated with
19 high and low confidence, respectively. Indeed, a sensitivity analysis based on the FEM presented in SI1 confirms this
20 experimental finding. The two datasets complement each other and allow extraction of the 3D dopant profile with
21 overall high confidence. The values obtained for the depth of the top and bottom layers, and the maxima of their
22 dopant densities are in good agreement with values obtained independently on non-patterned samples by SIMS and
23 Hall-bar measurements^{14,32} respectively. Thus, in addition to the benefits bb-EFM offers over SMM and other related
24 techniques, these results not only prove that the technique retains the ability to quantitatively determine depth and
25 sheet resistance, but the results in Table 1, in fact, show a factor of 2 improvement in measurement accuracy compared
26 with SMM¹⁴. Based on modelling discussed in the SI (Extended Data Figure 7), the sensitivity of the bb-EFM
27 technique to buried dopants is expected to be strongest at medium to high doping levels ($> 5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), while low
28 and medium dopant densities lead to a decrease in lateral resolution.

29 **Electrical characteristics of carrier types and traps**

30 In addition to the local carrier profile, the carrier type can also be inferred from the $C'(V)$ curve. As shown in Fig. 4a
31 and Extended Data Figure 8 the application of a bias to the tip or the substrate mainly modulates the carrier distribution
32 between the surface and the highly doped δ -layer, while the electron concentration in the delta layer and below
33 changes only slightly. When negative voltages are applied to n-type delta-doping, electrons above the delta layer are
34 repelled from the surface, while for positive voltages they are attracted towards the surface. In contrast, for the $C'(V)$
35 curve obtained on the p-type boron pattern, C' rises for negative voltages where the holes are attracted towards the

1 surface and falls for positive bias where the holes are repelled (see Fig. 4c). The $C'(V)$ curve is therefore essential to
 2 identify the carrier type and complements the C' image. Note that we measured the $C'(V)$ curves at 1 MHz to remove
 3 any capacitive contribution from interface traps, which become visible at lower frequencies, as discussed below.
 4 Table 2 displays the results of the δ -layer dopant density and vertical peak position quantification using FEM,
 5 as described above. We note that while the P and B doped regions show clearly different $C'(V)$ curves, the region
 6 containing mixed P and B doping is dominated by the phosphorus response and is almost indistinguishable from the
 7 pure phosphorus region. The n-type (counter)doping seems to completely eradicate the p-type contrast. Although the
 8 single-species-pattern B and P measured depths h are hardly distinguishable (Table 2), this observation in the mixed-
 9 species-pattern might be explained by an enhanced segregation of the P atoms towards the surface during Si
 10 overgrowth²⁸ compared to the B atoms. In this way, the P atoms could effectively shield contributions to the response
 11 from the B dopants. This is confirmed by simulated $C'(V)$ curves from different overlapping B and P dopant
 12 distribution widths displayed in Extended Data Figure 9. This hypothesis can be further supported by the SIMS profiles
 13 in Skeren et al.⁷, and would also explain the overall lower signal contrast on B compared to P observed in Fig. 2.
 14 In addition to determining the carrier type, frequency dependent C' measurements provide information about
 15 imperfections such as oxide-interface charges or interface traps near the surface of the Si. Such imperfections are of
 16 great practical significance because they can lead to reductions in semiconductor device performance¹⁵. While fixed
 17 oxide charges Q_{ox} either repel or attract carriers and thus effectively add to the applied potential in the $C'(V)$ curve,
 18 interface traps Q_{it} can trap holes as well as electrons and thus modify the $C'(V)$ spectra in a more complex way^{29,33}.
 19 These interface traps can be effectively modelled as an additional capacitance C_{it} in parallel with the depletion
 20 capacitance C_{dep} (see Fig.4a). Since interface traps can only follow low frequency alternating electric fields, it has
 21 been shown by Castagné-Vapaille using standard, on wafer capacitance voltage spectroscopy³⁵, that by comparing
 22 high and low frequency $C(V)$ s, the density of interface states can be successfully extracted following the equation:

$$23 \quad D_{it} = \frac{c_{ox}}{A Q} \left(\frac{c_{lf}}{c_{ox}-c_{lf}} - \frac{c_{hf}}{c_{ox}-c_{hf}} \right) \quad (3)$$

24 Here C_{ox} is the oxide capacitance, Q the elementary charge, and C_{lf} and C_{hf} the low and high frequency capacitances,
 25 respectively. The term in parenthesis is just a ratio and the capacitance C_{ox} in the first term can be normalized by the
 26 area to $c_{ox}=C_{ox}/A$. Thus, we can adapt this equation to our measurements by exchanging the capacitance variables
 27 with our measured capacitance gradient data C' at low and high frequency, respectively:

$$28 \quad D_{it} = \frac{c_{ox}}{Q} \left(\frac{c'_{lf}}{c'_{lf,ac}-c'_{lf}} - \frac{c'_{hf}}{c'_{hf,ac}-c'_{hf}} \right) \quad (4)$$

29 While the oxide capacitance in the parenthesis corresponds to the capacitance gradient measured in accumulation C_{ac}' ,
 30 we calculate the value for c_{ox} assuming an oxide thickness of 2 nm and an $\epsilon_r=3.8$. In this way, we directly obtain
 31 quantitative values of D_{it} from our measurements without the need of FEM. We measured $C'(V)$ curves at four
 32 frequencies from 1 kHz to 1 MHz and visualize the signal $C(V,f)$ in Fig. 4e in a contour plot. We use Eq. 4 to calculate
 33 $D_{it}(V)$ from the high (100 kHz) and low (1kHz) frequency data. Trap densities obtained for Si in this way agree with
 34 values typically reported in literature on native Si/SiO₂ interfaces³⁶. For the P δ -layer we observe an increase of D_{it} at
 35 positive gate voltages with a maximum of up to $D_{it}=1.5 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ eV}^{-1}$ (cf. Fig. 4d). This higher density of interface

1 traps above the P delta-layer is related to surface segregation of the phosphorus dopants, which increase the lattice
2 mismatch and induce the formation of trivalent Si atoms which act as amphoteric traps²⁹. Interestingly, we observe a
3 significantly lower trap density of $D_{it}=0.7 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ eV}^{-1}$ above the boron δ -layer which can again be explained by the
4 lower surface segregation of boron compared to phosphorus.

5 Finally, from $C'(f)$ -spectra acquired at 0V bias at different sample locations (Fig. 4f), we find that the interface traps
6 mainly affect the capacitance data in the low frequency range below 1 MHz. For frequencies above this value, our
7 $C'(V)$ model, ignoring interface traps, fits well to the data. At lower frequencies we see a clear deviation between
8 model and experiment, especially for Si, where we observe a decay at 1-10 MHz related to the time constant $\tau \sim R_x C_{si}$.
9 Only when we consider interface trapping, shown with the dashed lines, does our model converge better with the
10 experimental data. This result both confirms the presence of interface traps, and demonstrates the strength of bb-EFM
11 in its ability to detect and quantify such traps.

13 Conclusions

15 We have shown that bb-EFM can be used to determine both the 3D position and the carrier density of buried
16 dopant nanostructures within a silicon wafer. The technique can simultaneously distinguish regions of
17 atomically thin n-type and p-type doping, as well as distinguish trapped charges from mobile carriers induced
18 by dopants and local gating. The technique operates in tapping mode, is non-destructive and allows the
19 pinpointing of the lateral and vertical positions of δ -layers with 10 nm and 0.5 nm resolution, respectively.
20 This is a factor five better than the resolution reported previously for SMM¹⁴ and a factor of ten better than
21 reported for SCM³⁷ on similar samples. The improved resolution is due to a high sensitivity of 1 pF/m and
22 the ability to sense the local capacitance gradients across a wide frequency range from 1 kHz to 10 GHz. This
23 allows interface traps in regions containing different dopant types to be identified.

24 In the devices tested here, the bb-EFM data reveals that there is likely a significant segregation of phosphorus
25 towards the surface, whereas the boron remains well confined — a fabrication issue that could be solved by
26 growing a locking layer to limit the segregation³⁸. When combined with semiconductor finite element
27 modelling for parameter quantification, this approach could be used as a diagnostic imaging tool for the next
28 generation of classical and quantum devices. Furthermore, the ability to detect the insertion of hardware
29 Trojans¹, particularly when implemented below the gate level, would be invaluable for the security sector. It
30 has been shown that by changing the dopant polarity of existing transistors, the cryptographically secure
31 function of certain Intel processors can be compromised³⁹. This Trojan could not be detected using optical
32 reverse engineering since only the dopant masks were modified. While non-destructive X-ray tomography of
33 integrated circuits^{3,4} can provide full three-dimensional images not provided by the bb-EFM (which cannot
34 look underneath metallic screening layers), the X-ray technique is insensitive to the electrons and holes
35 directly responsible for chip functionality. We believe these techniques are complementary and could be used
36 in tandem for non-destructive chip inspection.

1

2 **Methods**

3 **Sample preparation**

4

5 The 3D phosphorus sample was fabricated in an Omicron VT-STM system with a base pressure of less than 2×10^{-10}
6 mbar. An n-type (15 Ωcm , 500 μm thickness) arsenic doped Si (100) wafer with deep etched registration markers was cut
7 into $9 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ samples. After a pre-UHV chemical clean with acetone and isopropanol the sample was loaded into vacuum,
8 thermally cleaned and passivated with hydrogen in a standard process³⁹. Electrons from a STM tip were used to de-
9 passivate a bar shaped area of $3.5 \times 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ followed by a saturation dosage of PH_3 (0.09 L). This results in a molecular
10 adsorption of PH_3 exclusively in the hydrogen evacuated region⁴⁰. Subsequently, second (0.003 L) and third (0.002 L)
11 bars were lithographically defined on the surface following the same procedure. The three bars with locally different
12 dopant densities are encapsulated with 5 nm of silicon by molecular beam epitaxy from a Si sublimation source. Si growth
13 included a so called locking layer technique³⁷ that was developed to reduce P dopant segregation. Following this process,
14 the first 10 monolayers of the sample were grown at a low sample temperature of $\sim 60^\circ\text{C}$. A subsequent short rapid thermal
15 anneal of 15 s at 500°C incorporates the P atoms into the surface³¹, making them electrically active. For further Si growth
16 the sample temperature was kept at 250°C . A constant deposition rate of 1 monolayer per minute was used throughout.
17 After reaching the final thickness, a 2-min anneal to 450°C flattens the surface making it suitable for high quality hydrogen
18 passivation and subsequent lithography steps. The three bars in the top layer were patterned and dosed with the same
19 parameters as the bottom layer bars, but rotated by 90° .

20 The combined boron and phosphorus sample was prepared on a Si(100) wafer (1.5 Ωcm , 500 μm thickness). The Si
21 surface was cleaned, and passivated with hydrogen in ultra-high vacuum, using a standard process³⁹. Patterns of clean Si
22 are written by de-passivating the Si(100)- $2 \times 1:\text{H}$ surface⁴¹ using the electron beam from an STM tip as for the other above
23 sample. The patterned surface was first exposed to a background PH_3 pressure of $\sim 1 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar for 2 min which resulted
24 in adsorption of the PH_3 molecules exclusively within the de-passivated regions⁴⁰. Subsequently, the STM was used again
25 to de-passivate an additional region and exposed to a background B_2H_6 pressure of $\sim 1 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar again for 2 min. The
26 phosphorus and boron atoms were incorporated into the surface via a 2 min anneal at 350°C ²⁶ and subsequently the
27 donor nanostructure is encapsulated with 15 nm of silicon, grown by molecular beam epitaxy from a Si sublimation
28 source. A low sample temperature of $\approx 250^\circ\text{C}$ during Si sublimation provides both a low donor surface segregation and
29 relatively smooth Si crystal growth⁴². Further details on the sample preparation are given in⁷.

30

31 **Experimental Setup**

32 The experimental setup for 3D dopant profiling is shown in Fig. 1 and consists of a 5600 AFM (Keysight Technologies,
33 USA) operated in tapping mode and interfaced with a signal generator through a coaxial cable and tip holder capable of
34 delivering high frequency signals up to the tip (SMM nose cone). Additionally, a bias voltage can be applied to the tip or
35 the substrate. We used a MXG5183B analogue signal generator to cover a frequency range from 1 kHz to 10 GHz. A
36 sinusoidal voltage signal with an angular frequency f_{carrier} is applied between a conductive probe and the bottom of the
37 sample and the force in eq (1) is measured.

1 We found that PtSi-FM cantilevers (Nanosensors, Germany) with a nominal spring constant of 2.8 N/m and a resonance
2 frequency of 67 kHz offer the best trade-off between mechanical stability, wear resistance, and electrical conductivity.
3 We also tested highly doped Si and diamond probes (Nanosensors, Germany), standard Pt coated Si probes (Nanosensors,
4 Germany) and full Pt probes (RMN, USA). While the first two tips showed too low conductivity at frequencies above a
5 few MHz, the full Pt tips did not allow for stable tapping mode imaging at low amplitudes. The standard Pt coated tips
6 tended to wear off and modify very quickly, which is disadvantageous for calibration. When the carrier frequency is
7 beyond the mechanical resonance of the cantilever, the cantilever continues to bend statically due to the non-linear
8 dependence of the actuation force on the applied voltage. Amplitude modulation of the carrier at a low frequency, f_{mod} , of
9 about 1 kHz leads to an oscillation of the down-modulated force, which is detected with an enhanced S/N ratio by a lock-
10 in amplifier sensing directly at the modulation frequency f_{mod} or by demodulating the phase shift of the mechanical
11 cantilever oscillation at f_{mod} .
12 Frequency calibration has been carried out as in ⁴³. In short, an image is acquired on the region of interest in lift-mode at
13 three different lift-heights from the surface (eg. 20 nm, 30 nm, 50 nm). While the x-scan is active the y-scan is stopped
14 and the measurement frequency is changed at every new line, producing a frequency spectrum for every lift height.
15 Extrapolation of the scanning distance defines the background of the frequency spectrum, which is used to normalize the
16 data. Measurements have been carried out in a dry nitrogen atmosphere.

17 18 **Finite Element Modelling**

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20 FEM was carried out with *COMSOL Multiphysics 5.4* (2D axisymmetric, electrostatics + semiconductor module,
21 semiconductor equilibrium, frequency domain perturbation). The simulation geometry for quantification resembles the
22 experimental conditions. The model consists of a 15 μ m high AFM tip modelled as a truncated cone with a cone angle θ
23 and cantilever extending the cone end by 10 μ m. The tip has a spherical apex with a radius R and is located at a distance
24 z above the sample. The sample comprises a 250 μ m thick Si substrate (we verified that the exact thickness is not relevant
25 for our calculations) with a constant background doping of $3 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the two different samples,
26 respectively. The additionally grown 15nm thick Si layer on the surface is modelled as being undoped. The P and B δ -
27 layers are modelled as acceptor and donor doping distributions with a Gaussian shape centred at h nm below the surface
28 with a $\sigma=1.5$ nm, and a lateral width corresponding to the area of the patterned δ -layer. To account for the segregation of
29 dopants towards the surface we model the region between tip and doping layer with a doping density 10 times smaller
30 than the peak value of the δ -layer. The probe-surrounding is air with the same size as the Si region. Fermi-Dirac-Statistics
31 were used to obtain correct results for the high dopant concentrations. Available mobility models Arora- and Fletcher-
32 Model were implemented. An SRH-generation recombination model was used. To achieve accurate results and
33 convergence of the solution, meshing was set to scale with the size of the involved geometries. In this way the mesh size
34 on the boundary of the apex and membrane was always at least 20 times smaller than the tip apex. The model was meshed
35 from the inside (apex + δ -layer region) to the outside (cone and surrounding area). Outside parts were meshed
36 automatically by *Comsol*. The downward directed Maxwell-Stress-Tensor in z direction was calculated from the small-
37 signal-solution on the tip boundaries which had been set to Terminal. From these data the capacitance gradient was
38 calculated. To determine the tip-geometry a combination of experiments and simulations was carried out^{13,44}. In detail,
39 electrostatic force approach curves (z from 2-500 nm) were simulated for a wide range of tip radii, R , and cone angle, θ .

1 Using a fitting procedure with the simulated approach curves, the tip radius and cone angle are extracted that lead to the
2 best agreement with the experimental approach curve.
3 After the estimation of the tip geometry, the capacitance gradient C' was calculated for a wide range of dopant
4 concentrations ρ and depth h , changing the measurement parameters bias V , frequency f , and tip sample distance z ,
5 respectively, while keeping the geometry fixed. A lookup table/ interpolation function was generated from this data to fit
6 the simulated to the experimental data. The fitting results are ρ and depth h . Note that the calculated forces from the small
7 signal-solution assumes small AC-voltages $<1V$ to satisfy the harmonic perturbation approach. To relate experiments
8 obtained at excitation voltages of 2-3V with the simulations, an additional integration-differentiation step over the
9 experimental voltage range is necessary.

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12 **Data Availability**

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14 All data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and/or the Supplementary Materials.
15 Additional data related to this paper may be requested from the authors. The data created during this research are openly
16 available at le at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3899692>

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26

27 **Author contributions**

28 GG conceived and designed the experiments, performed the experiments, analysed the data, wrote the paper. AK
29 performed the experiments, contributed materials/analysis tools, wrote the paper. TS contributed materials/analysis
30 tools, wrote the paper, GA conceived and designed the experiments, wrote the paper, FK conceived and designed the

1 experiments, AF contributed materials/analysis tools, conceived and designed the experiments, wrote the paper. NJ
2 conceived and designed the experiments, wrote the paper.

3 **Competing interests**

4 There are no conflicts to declare.

5 **Additional information**

6 **Supplementary Information**

7 **Extended Data**

8 **Supplementary Information**

9

10 Supplementary Figures 1-2, Note 1

1 **Table 1** Doping profiling results on 3D P-sample obtained from FEM calculations and experimental data.
 2 Results correspond to fittings shown in Fig. 3. P- δ -layer at $h=15\text{nm}$ in Si $3\times 10^{14}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ As doped.

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SIMS $\rho (10^{20}\text{ cm}^{-3})/h(\text{nm})$	$\rho (10^{20}\text{ cm}^{-3})$		$h (\text{nm})$	
	$C'(V)$	$C'(z)$	$C'(V)$	$C'(z)$
$7.6\pm 0.1/3.8\text{nm}$	7 ± 2	9 ± 8	3 ± 1	4.3 ± 0.4
$0.5\pm 0.1/3.8\text{nm}$	0.5 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.5	5 ± 1	4.1 ± 0.7
$1.7\pm 0.1/8.9\text{ nm}$	1.7 ± 0.9	5 ± 4	8 ± 2	8.5 ± 0.5
$0.5\pm 0.1/8.9\text{ nm}$	0.7 ± 0.2	-	9 ± 2	-

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5 **Table 2** Doping profiling results obtained from FEM calculations and experimental data of P and B sample.
 6 Results correspond to fits shown in Fig. 4c. P/B- δ -layer at $h=15\text{nm}$ in Si $3\times 10^{15}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ As doped.

Dopant	$\rho (10^{20}\text{ cm}^{-3})$		$h (\text{nm})$	
	$C'(V)$	$C'(z)$	$C'(V)$	$C'(z)$
<i>B</i>	5.8 ± 0.4	5.3 ± 4	15 ± 3	15 ± 0.9
<i>B+P</i>	6.1 ± 0.6	-	13 ± 3	-
<i>P</i>	6.7 ± 0.7	6.1 ± 3	14 ± 2	14 ± 0.8

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8 **Figure 1** Broadband electrostatic force microscope for 3D dopant profiling. Electrostatic force (change of capacitance
 9 derivative $\Delta C'(z)$) on a conductive AFM probe is measured to obtain the 2D footprint of a buried dopant layer with
 10 nanometre lateral resolution. Doping profile in the vertical dimension is obtained by probing $\Delta C'$ as a function of
 11 sample bias V_{bias} , probe sample distance z and measurement frequency. Finite Element Model (FEM) shown on the
 12 bottom right is used to extract quantitative information. For frequency dependent measurements, a signal generator
 13 delivers an amplitude modulated signal to the AFM probe with a fixed kHz modulation frequency and a carrier
 14 frequency $f_{carrier}$ between 100 kHz and 10 GHz. The induced electrostatic force is recovered through the lock-in
 15 amplifier (LIA) by direct amplitude modulation. Electrostatic force images are acquired together with topography in
 16 tapping mode.

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4 **Figure 2** Patterned boron and phosphorus δ -layer structure buried $h=15$ nm below the surface. a) Overlay of AFM
5 topography and $\Delta C'(z)$ -image. b) $\Delta C'(z)$ image of boron resolution test patterns (stripes have a constant gap of 60 nm
6 and decreasing width from the left to the right 2x32 nm, 2x16 nm, 3x8 nm, 5x4 nm). Corresponding $\Delta C'(z)$ profile
7 lines are shown in c). Red lines show fitting with a logistic function as detailed in the text. PtSi-FM tips from
8 NanoSensors (Germany) with nominal tip radius of $R=30$ nm were used ($V_{bias}=0$ V, $V_{ac}=1.5$ V, $f_{carrier}=242$ kHz).

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4 **Figure 3** Quantitative dopant profiling of a phosphorus patterned sample. a) Left: C' image of test sample
 5 acquired at $f_{\text{carrier}}=1\text{ GHz}$, $z=24\text{nm}$, $V_{\text{bias}}=0\text{V}$. Right: Schematic cross-section of the 3D test sample. b)
 6 Normalized capacitance versus voltage curves acquired on locations indicated in a). Black solid lines
 7 represent best fit of finite element model (FEM) calculated C' curves to experimental data as detailed in the
 8 text ($f_{\text{carrier}}=1\text{GHz}$, $z=22\text{nm}$). c) Simplified equivalent circuit model of P δ -layer (where R_x = bulk resistance,
 9 R_{sh} = delta-layer sheet resistance, and h = depth of the δ -layer below the surface) and finite element model of
 10 the AFM tip 10nm above the surface containing P δ -layer (potential distribution is shown in colors). The
 11 conduction band energy minus the Fermi energy level is plotted along the symmetry axis for dopant
 12 concentration of $3 \times 10^{18}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ (dotted lines) and $3 \times 10^{21}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ (solid lines) for different biases (3V- red, 0V -
 13 orange, -3V black). d) Capacitance approach curves and FEM fitting ($f_{\text{carrier}}=1\text{GHz}$, $V_{\text{bias}}=0\text{V}$). Symbols are
 14 color-coded as in the schematic at right of a).

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2 **Figure 4** Dynamics and interface traps. a) Simulated carrier distribution (electrons) for a bias of -3V and +3V. Below
3 equivalent circuit model also accounting for traps in the oxide-semiconductor interface. b) C' image showing the
4 locations where $C'(V, f)$ experiments were carried out. c) $C'(V)$ spectra acquired at 1MHz, at the positions indicated in
5 b). Three sweeps were averaged, single data traces are available in Extended Data Figure 10 showing reproducibility.
6 d) Calculated interface-trap density as detailed in the text. e) Frequency dependent $C'(V)$ spectra on the four sample
7 locations indicated in b). The y-axes in these contour-plots show the measurement frequency with logarithmic spacing
8 from 1kHz to 1MHz. f) Normalized $C'(f)$ spectra measured over seven orders of magnitude at $V_{bias}=0V$ (normalization
9 by C'_{bg} is detailed in the Experimental Section). Dashed lines correspond to fitting with calculated $C'(f)$ from FEM
10 including interface traps, while solid lines do not take interface traps into account.

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